

STELLENBOSCH UNIVERSITY

DEPARTMENT OF CONSERVATION ECOLOGY AND ENTOMOLOGY

**A SOCIO-ECOLOGICAL STUDY OF THE WOLFGAT
NATURE RESERVE AND THE NEIGHBOURING
MITCHELLS PLAIN COMMUNITY**

EXPLORING THE THREAT THAT CRIME POSES TO THE CONSERVATION
USING NEWSPAPER CONTENT AND STAKEHOLDER NETWORK
ANALYSIS

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A socio-ecological study of the Wolfgat Nature Reserve and the neighbouring Mitchells Plain community:

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By

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Abstract

Wolfgat Nature Reserve, experiences a severe security threat level due to violent crime as a result of its location and the social challenges facing the Cape Flats community of Mitchell's Plain. The WNR has for a long period of time, received largely negative newspaper coverage. Mitchell's Plain experiences immense socio-economic pressures, such as high unemployment, a flourishing gang controlled criminal economy and extremely high levels of drug abuse, which has further torn its social fabric, as a result of underdevelopment and isolation as a result of old government policies such as those of Apartheid.

190 newspaper articles published between 1994 and 2013 were analysed using, content, narrative and stakeholder analysis, to determine the nature of the coverage of Wolfgat in the news as well as the context wherein these events occurred.

The lack of social control, inadequate law enforcement capacity and underdevelopment, to which the community, law enforcement and the local government are central, were found to be the underlying cause for the threat WNR experiences due to violent crime in particular.

The success of an urban nature reserve such as WNR is thus highly contingent on the success of the Mitchells Plain community. It is difficult to separate the criminal threats facing the reserve and the community from the development of the area. For the criminal threat faced by the WNR to be effectively addressed, the socio-economic development needs of the community need to be met and effective crime prevention and control strategies implemented. For the conservation of WNR to be successful in overcoming the threat posed by crime, the local community needs to be mobilised to take control of the area, by enforcing social control and creating a defensible space in collaboration with the central stakeholders' such as SAPS, the City of Cape Town and the Nature Conservation staff of WNR.

Introduction

In the City of Cape Town's Management plan for Wolfgat Nature Reserve (WNR) on the False Bay coast, crime, its increased incidence and the associated threats like intimidation of conservation staff and its implications on the safety and security of the reserve, have been identified as a threat not only to conservation of WNR but also to the neighbouring community of Mitchell's Plain in the Cape Flats (Walters, 2011). The security audit for the City of Cape Town's nature reserves has cited that WNR experiences a severe security threat level due to violent crime due to its location and the social challenges faced by the neighbouring community (Phelan and Thornhill, 2010).

WNR has built up a reputation over the years, not for its scenic beauty or biodiversity but rather for the criminal activities known to be associated with it, hence its ill fame of forming part of the Cape Flats "Bushes of Evil" (CCT, 2009; Rebelo et al., 2011). Media reports, particularly in the form of newspaper articles, have created awareness of the high incidence of crime that have occurred, or are associated with this area. Violent crime, which includes murder, rape, gang related violence and assault of conservation staff, associated with the reserve has thus become public knowledge, through the printed press, namely, newspapers. Crime and gangsterism has been determined to be the biggest factor deterring the local community from using the reserve, whilst acting as a barrier to conservation staff, preventing them from accessing the conservation area regularly to perform duties (Manuel, 2006; Phelan & Thornhill, 2010; Walters, 2011).

Wolfgat Nature Reserve is an urban reserve neighbouring Cape Towns, two largest townships, namely Mitchell's Plain and Khayelitsha, which are also amongst the largest in the country. It's the reserves close proximity to these areas have put the reserve under great risk of being subjected to the social challenges faced by these areas (SACN, 2003). This part of the City of Cape Town experiences high levels of unemployment, social decay and crime. Challenges that could be attributed to the legacy left behind by the Apartheid government, that have been further worsened by the failure of current governance strategies in terms of development and crime prevention and law enforcement in this Cape Flats township of Mitchell's Plain (Samara, 2011).

The SWOT analysis of the WNR Management Plan (Walters, 2011), identified that criminal

and associated safety and security threats, such as poor presence of law enforcement, the lack of patrols and the increased incidence of crime, brought about by the social challenges facing the neighbouring community, lay outside the control of the CCT nature conservation department and its staff.

The aim of this research is to explore the impact that the social challenge of crime, faced by the Mitchell's Plain community poses a threat towards the conservation and management of the Wolfgat Nature Reserve and how the both the challenges and the reserve itself contributes to the pervasiveness of crime in the area. By making use of a newspaper article content analysis, in combination with a narrative analysis of the article content and a stakeholder network analysis (SNA), to determine the coverage of issues according to theme over a near 20 year period from 1994 until 2013 reported in all available newspaper articles. To identify and describe the significance of events and issues as it relates the threat and challenge posed by crime to conservation, as well as the stakeholders that are most central to theme.

Wolfgat Nature Reserve

Named after the fossilized brown hyena den discovered in its limestone cliffs in 1962, the WNR was established as a nature reserve in 1986 by the then Parks and Forest Branch, City Engineering Department and the City Of Cape Town. And now forms a crucial part of the City's biodiversity network (Walters, 2011; City of Cape Town, 2007; Graham and Ernstson, 2012).

Prior to its establishment, from as early as the 1970s, the protection of the Cape Flats Dune Strandveld vegetation subtype at WNR was described as vital. This is due to its protective and regulatory function, such as maintaining a stable inland climate and offering protection against environmental disturbances such as wind erosion and wave action, in so ensuring the protection of infrastructure (Brand, 1979).

It comprises an endemic and endangered vegetation subtype known as Cape Flats Dune Strandveld (Rebelo et al., 2011), which is rapidly approaching critically endangered status. This is in part due to alien invasive such as *Acacia cyclops* (Rooikrans) and *A. saligna* (Port Jackson), but mostly due to the increased pressures of urbanisation and issue related to urban decay (Walters, 2011; Rebelo et al., 2011).

A unique site, the 248 ha WNR is home to the only limestone cliffs on the False Bay coastline, and is one of only three land-based breeding grounds for the Kelp gulls (Walters, 2011). The WNR boasts approximately 178 plant species, including a protected stand of the endangered White Milkwood trees (*Sideroxylon inerme*) (Cape Flats Nature, 2010). It is also home to a diverse spread of fauna, including a wide range of small animals (Walters, 2011). Prior to the construction and development of Mitchell's Plain in the 1970s, the City along with the Department of Nature Conservation embarked on what was dubbed "Operation Noah", with the purpose of removing fauna and flora from the area (Brand, 1979). The coastal area of the reserve provides a habitat for a range of marine life including fish, seals, great white sharks, and dolphins, and for the seasonal migration of several species of whale known to breed in False Bay (Bodenstein and Rippon, 2001; Graham and Ernstson, 2012).

Wolfgat Nature Reserve forms a crucial part of the City's Biodiversity Network. The success of this area will thus also affect the greater success of the network. It also forms a strategic part of the city's development and management frameworks for the Mitchell's Plain area and surrounds.

Mitchell's Plain

Mitchell's plain was originally designed to be a model town for housing coloured residents under the Group Areas Act of 1955 during the Apartheid regime. It was the first of its kind in South Africa, post-World War 2. Prior to its establishment, housing for the largely poor and oppressed coloured communities consisted of large blocks of flats, in close proximity to one another. It was established that this design facilitated criminal activity and perpetuated poverty through overcrowding and poor living conditions (Brand, 1979).

Mitchell's Plain was designed to house 250 000 individuals in 40 000 dwellings or homes of which residents would be able to acquire ownership (this was not possible with the previous housing schemes, where residents were only tenants who rented space). The 3 100 ha town is located approximately 27 km south-east of the Cape Town central business district, and was selected as it was the only land of suitable size for such a large-scale development (Human, 1977; Brand, 1979).

In 1971, 3 years before the construction of Mitchell's Plain officially commenced, the coloured population of the Cape Town municipal area was approximately 366 000 (Human,

1977). This means that, by its completion in 1984, Mitchell's Plain was essentially designed to house approximately 68% of the coloured population in this municipal area.

Many estimates exist as to what the population size is today, which may range from 512 000 (Manuel, 2011) to more than a million individuals (City of Cape Town, 2012). With this increase in population size, living conditions have deteriorated and social problems often associated with social decay have increased in their severity. Unemployment, substance abuse and gangsterism, as well as increases in criminal activity, have become ever more worrying. Previous studies (Everatt and Smith, 2008; Mac Kay, 2006) have shown that crime and safety are some of the most prevalent issues facing the community. Crime and safety and their relation to the issues of substance abuse, gangsterism and unemployment form the core of social challenges facing the community. These issues have had a strong negative influence on the ability of the town of Mitchell's Plain to develop into a socially coherent and economically productive community.

Social problems, such as substance abuse, crime and unemployment tend to have dire effects on a society's ability to function optimally, and in the case of Mitchell's Plain this is clear (Everatt and Smith, 2008). These effects are far-reaching and are felt in relation to decision making on social, political, economic and environmental fronts. These problems do not exist in isolation but also affects various aspects of society, including its politics and economics, as well as affecting the built and natural environment adjacent to it. It is therefore not surprising that the City of Cape Town Municipality has found that the vacant areas within the Cape Flats do in fact harbour criminal elements (Phelan and Thornhill, 2010).

The Department of Local Government (2004) described Mitchell's Plain as an area that is isolated and dysfunctional, characterised by overcrowding, many social evils and limited opportunities' for economic growth. Coupled with this, Mitchell's Plain has been described as having no economic base, apart from informal and small formal economies (DPLG, 2001).

Urban renewal in Mitchell's Plain, Cape Town

Urban renewal in South Africa is a complex process that involves contending with a combination of challenges that include high crime rates, an increase in inequality and a growing public frustration with regards to the renewal process (Samara, 2005). The city

planners of Cape Town, in an attempt to stimulate economic growth and improve the city's competitive ability on the global platform, have cited crime as the primary threat to the urban renewal process. Despite attempts to reduce levels of crime, urban renewal programmes have not yet made any significant changes (Samara, 2011).

Mitchell's Plain, which borders WNR, is one of the areas that have been selected as URP nodes. The area experiences a severe criminal threat, particularly in the Tafelsig area, which has been identified as a Cape (provincial) Renewal Node due to its high levels of crime and gang activity (CRS, 2002 Tafelsig Precinct Development Plan and the associated social, economic and other conditions which perpetuate this form of criminality (Executive Summary of Seven Precinct Development Plans, Dec 2002). Tafelsig is of special concern to this paper, as it is the subsection of Mitchell's Plain that borders the entire northern boundary of WNR.

The Tafelsig Precinct Plan that forms part of the Cape Renewal Strategy identified and categorised all the key safety problems according to the proposed "crime and unsafe environment" projects designed to tackle them. The categories were as follows: 1) degraded or unsafe public open spaces; 2) insufficient policing services and capacity; and 3) insufficient traffic-calming measures. Other challenges identified were lack of sporting facilities, a high unemployment rate, insufficient educational facilities and a lack of youth activities (Cape Renewal Strategy, 2002; Rauch, 2002)—challenges also echoed by others (URDR, 2004; Everatt & Smith, 2007; DPLG, 2004; Haefele, 2011).

Poverty and relative deprivation are often considered to driving forces behind the escalating crime rate in South Africa, giving rise to the perspective that the solutions lie in investment, economic growth and the creation of jobs to curb unemployment. However, while such "development" may present a solution to the problem of crime, at the same time the magnitude of the problem that crime poses is undermining those very developmental initiatives (Rauch, 2002).

Mitchell's Plain experiences severe economic challenges, high levels of substance abuse, violent crime and disrupted families and broken homes, all of which are elements contributing to its social disorganisation, particularly in communities such as Tafelsig, on the border of WNR (Haefele, 2011; URDR, 2004; Everatt & Smith, 2008). According to the Department of Local Government (2004), Mitchell's Plain can be described as an area that

is “isolated and dysfunctional, whilst being overcrowded, having many social evils and limited opportunities” for economic growth. Much of this can be owed to the apartheid legacy (Khan, 2000) and the poor design of the area that actively prohibited economic initiatives left the community isolated from the Cape Town economy (Everatt & Smith, 2008).

Methods and Materials

Wolfgat Nature Reserve experiences a severe security threat due to violent crime as result of its location and the social challenges of its neighbouring community.

Aims: To explore the Impact that crime and the social challenges faced by the Mitchell’s Plain community poses a threat towards the conservation and management of the Wolfgat Nature Reserve, from a development perspective using newspaper content and stakeholder network analysis and the role of the reserve area to the pervasiveness of crime.

Research questions:

How does crime act as a security threat to conservation and what are the conditions; social, economic and environmental that allows crime to be so pervasive in the WNR?

What are the categories of issues reported in newspapers that WNR faces?

What is the level of importance newspaper articles referring to WNR place on the nature reserve?

Is there relationship between Importance placed on WNR within the article and the category of the reported issue specific to WNR. (Purely methodological for use in the narrative analysis of the news articles)

Is there a relationship between the WNR specific theme and the year of publication? With regards to the issues that have been categorised, do patterns exist? At which year were certain issues more prominent?

Who are the most important and central stakeholders with in the network of events reported within the newspapers? Measures based on raw count (no. of references- degree) and others. Placement with in a network connecting stakeholders through reported issues.

Methods

In order to answer these questions I made use of newspaper content analysis, which sought to extract information related to the reported issue within the article as it relates to WNR. The extracted information was largely manifest, and included the following variables-general article theme, and theme of the issues with specific to WNR within the article and the date of publication. Other variables that were incorporated in to the data analysis include the level of importance placed on WNR within the article, and stakeholder details that are manifest in the news content.

Determining the categories of themes of the news articles

From a total of 286 newspaper articles, 190 articles, from 17 community, local and regional newspaper publications sourced from SA Media, Independent Newspapers, Media 24 and Issuu digital archives using the search term 'wolfgat' and 'Wolfgat', were analysed. The process of removal of duplicate articles as well as the exclusion of articles and content that are not news articles, editorials, columns or news reports, limited the analysis to 190 articles. For which, publication date and source were recorded. Each article was given a unique ID code, in order to retrace articles for use in the narrative analysis of the content

A content analysis process was used to derive the themes of the articles based on its content, namely the discussed and listed issues referring to the WNR. This research method is commonly used to analyse written, verbal or visual communication messages (Cole, 1988). This research method is systematic and objective means of describing and quantifying phenomena (Krippendorff, 1980; Downe-Wamboldt, 1992; Sandelowski, 1995). And is a well-known method of analysing documents, like newspaper publications.

It allows for the testing of theoretical issues that enhance the understanding of the data. Content analysis allows words or content to be distilled into fewer content related categories or themes, under the assumption that when classified into the same categories, words, phrases and the like share the same meaning (Cavanagh, 1997).

This research method is used for making replicable and valid inferences from data to their context, the purpose of which is to provide knowledge, new insights, a representation of facts or information, which may contribute to creating a practical guide to action (Krippendorff, 1980).

The aim in using this method is thus to attain a condensed and broad description of the phenomenon, which in this case are the issues facing the conservation of Wolfgat Nature Reserve, with a specific focus on crime and the social challenges of the neighbouring community that contributes towards it. The purpose of those concepts or categories that arise in this process is to build up a conceptual map or categories, which can be used to explain the phenomenon that is the criminal threat of violent crime that faces WNR. An inductive content analysis process was used to determine the categories (article themes) used within this research, adopted from Elo and Kyngas (2007):

This process includes a series of steps comprising of: open coding, creating categories and abstraction. Open coding means that notes and headings are written in the text while reading it. The written material is read through again, and as many headings as necessary are written down in the margins to describe all aspects of the content (Burnard, 1991; Hsieh & Shannon, 2005). For the purpose of this study, information regarding the reported incident or issue discussed was recorded i.e. asking what happened. And who was involved (stakeholder)? The headings are then collected from the margins on to coding sheets (Cole, 1988; Downe-Wamboldt, 1992; Dey, 1993) and categories are freely generated at this stage (Burnard 1991). After this open coding, the lists of categories are grouped under higher order headings (McCain, 1988; Burnard, 1991). The aim of grouping data was to reduce the number of categories by collapsing those that are similar or dissimilar into broader higher order categories (Burnard, 1991; Downe-Wamboldt 1992; Dey, 1993). This can be described as the process of abstraction. The purpose of creating categories is to provide a means of describing the phenomenon, to increase understanding and to generate knowledge (Cavanagh, 1997). When formulating categories by inductive content analysis, the researcher comes to a decision, through interpretation, as to which things to put in the same category (Dey, 1993).

Another variable that was included was the 'level of importance' placed on WNR within the article. Values were inferred using the following criteria; 1) Focus of article, which asks the question, 'is the WNR the main focus of the article or central to the reported issue?' And 2) the extent to which matters related to WNR is discussed in the article, 'in what level of detail is WNR discussed? Is it merely listed? Was there a reference to a specific incident at WNR?' A rating was then given to each article to in accordance to these criteria, with 1 representing a high level of importance, 2, a medium level and 3, a low level of importance.

Using IBM's SPSS 21 (Statistical Programme for Social Sciences), the coded data was analysed to determine basic descriptive information, of each of the variables as well as the relationship between the 'level of importance' placed on Wolfgat within the article and the theme of the article based on the issue specific to WNR within the article. Article theme was then cross-tabulated with the year of publication, to identify the clustering of articles and identify patterns based on themes over time.

Stakeholder Network Analysis: Identify most central stakeholders

Stakeholder information was also extracted from the articles to perform a Stakeholder Network Analysis using Gephi 0.8.2 beta for use in developing a network model illustrating the relationship and interactions between stakeholders and events (the reported issue in the article) in relation to the article themes derived using the content analysis. The main purpose of which is to identify the most central stakeholders in the network, in terms of their interactions within the network. Additionally it was done to determine which themes a stakeholder is most well connected to and similarly to which group of themes.

The use of Social Network Analysis in social sciences has grown exponentially in recent decades (Borgatti & Foster, 2003). According to the network perspective it is assumed that: (1) relationships among actors are important; (2) actors are interdependent rather than autonomous; (3) a relationship between two actors represents a flow of material or non-material resources; and (4) network structures enhance or inhibit actors' ability to act (Wasserman & Faust 1994). SNA has been used in a wide variety of contexts and its recent use in natural sciences has been motivation for its inclusion in to the methodology so as to determine the relationship between actor and themes of articles and their role in groups of issues relating to conservation (Schneider et al., 2003; Crona & Bodin, 2006; Isaac et al., 2007; Ernstson et al., 2008; McAllister et al., 2008; Ramirez-Sanchez & Pinkerton, 2009).

Narrative analysis of content

The results of the above mentioned analysis were combined to perform a narrative inquiry or analysis on the data. Narrative analysis uses field texts, such as stories, autobiography, journals, and newspaper articles amongst others as the units of analysis to research. The narrative analysis research methods used to analyse data draw from structuralism and literary criticism in its use of story elements, structure, and organization. Narrative structure provides a theoretical framework for analysis through different elements: story, scene,

actors and agents, motives, and actions. While the focus of narrative analysis is on the individual story, by exploring a number of stories that cohere as a larger story - a metastory - a clearer understanding of the culture that produces a narrative can be achieved (Bishop, 2001). In order to help explain the implications of the events, the relationships between the events and the role of the stakeholders therein as it relates to the problem, which is the problem social challenges, and particularly that of crime threatens the conservation of WNR. Narrative analysis reveals social information and values, and it packages information and inferences (Garner et al., 1998). News narratives are anchored in cultural meaning, thus not only does the story of crime associated with WNR enter social consciousness through print media coverage, but also social consciousness influences print media coverage of crime associated with WNR.

Results

Article themes

The inductive content analysis of the news articles gave rise to three broad categories of article themes namely, 'Crime, safety and security', 'urban planning and socio-economic development and 'Conservation'.

The themes 'Crime, safety and security', incorporates articles whose issues centred on incidents of crime associated with the reserve; anti-crime initiatives; environmental crimes that is largely about illegal dumping of refuse which contributes a relatively small number of articles under this theme; law enforcement; drowning incidence, which is a safety concern; reporting on assault towards staff; and discussions of other, crime safety and security issues. Urban planning and socio-economic development', incorporates all articles that are associated with socio-economic development, such as community development initiatives, business and tourism development, urban development projects, urbanisation and housing developments, service delivery, or a matter relating to urban planning such as re-routing of roads. Finally the theme 'Conservation' is made up of articles whose prime focus was biodiversity related; articles describing developments that directly concern WNR conservation, either in that it's a conservation based initiative such and environmental education and community based initiatives such as community greening where conservation departments run the initiatives etc.

Descriptive outputs of the dataset in SPSS showed a skew towards the category Crime, safety and security, which constituted 51.2% (n=86) of the articles analysed (n=168) of the general theme of the article. Conservation related articles constituted 30.4% (n=51) and Urban planning 18.5 % (n=31). However, when considering the issues that are reported that is specific to Wolfgat Nature Reserve within the context of the articles (n=171), we find that the percentage contribution made to conservation increases to 35.1% (valid per cent), and the contribution towards Urban, planning and socio-economic development decreases to 12.1%. Crime, safety and security show very little change, with a slight increase to 52.9% (Table 1).

Table 1: the total frequency and percentage of articles based the reported issue that specifically references WNR within the news article.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
Valid	Crime, safety and security	92	48.4	52.9
	Conservation	61	32.1	35.1
	Urban planning and socioeconomic development	21	11.1	12.1
	Total	174	91.6	100.0
Missing	not applicable	16	8.4	
Total		190	100.0	

Table 2: represents 'Level of importance' of Wolfgat Nature Reserve within the context of the news articles (n=183). It appears that when WNR is discussed within the article, it is most likely of a high importance (55.2%) to the issue reported in the newspaper. However if it is not of high importance to it will most likely show a low level of importance (29.5%). This may suggest that WNR is newsworthy within itself.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	high	101	53.2	55.2	55.2
	medium	28	14.7	15.3	70.5
	low	54	28.4	29.5	100.0
	Total	183	96.3	100.0	
Missing	System	7	3.7		
Total		190	100.0		

The relationship between the level of importance of WNR within the context of the article and article theme that refers to an issue specific to WNR shows that the higher the level of importance of WNR to the article the more likely it is that the theme or category of the article will be about Crime, safety and security (Figure 1). The Cramers V (0.260), Chi2 (23.47) suggests that there is a significant relationship $p < 0.001$ between the two variables (n=173). This suggests that crime, safety and security issues associated with WNR, is more newsworthy then conservation or urban planning and socio-economic development related issues.

Figure 1: the importance placed on Wolfgat nature reserve according to the theme specific to the event, activity that occurred at Wolfgat Nature Reserve. The graph suggests that the higher the level of importance assigned to WNR the more likely that the topic will be related to ‘Crime, safety and security’. The Cramers V (0.260), χ^2 (23.47) suggests that there is a significant relationship $p < 0.001$ between the two variables. $n=173$.

The analysed data makes use of newspaper articles published since 1994 up until July 2013. Figure 2, which illustrates the clustering of issues (articles), by year, reported in the news since 1994 according to the 3 broad categories of themes, shows that there are large clustering events, in 1997, 2006 and 2010-2012 in conservation, and very little clustering in urban planning and socioeconomic development. Under Crime safety and security, clustering is greatest in the period 2010 to 2012.

Figure 2: a scatterplot showing the clustering of articles by year and theme.

Stakeholder analysis

The Social Network Analysis (SNA) identified three major stakeholders namely the City of Cape Town (CCT) municipality, South African Police Services (SAPS) and the community of Mitchell's Plain bordering the reserve WNR. According all three of the measures, degree, eigenvector and betweenness centrality, these three stakeholders are consistently the highest ranked (Table) suggesting that these stakeholders are the most central to the network and thus the most important stakeholders Other stakeholder groups that feature in the top ranked stakeholder list includes municipal departments and branches such as the CCT Biodiversity management branch, the nature conservation department and the National Sea Rescue institute (NSRI).

When comparing the difference between the three measurements used in the analysis, with the exception of SAPS, CCT and the community forming the top 3, the order of the stakeholders following them change, or even fall from the top ranked stakeholders, particularly the James Restoration Home (JRH) and the South African Broadcasting Corporation (SABC),

Table 3: The top 16 stakeholders based on each of the 3 measures of centrality as seen in figures 7, 8 and 9. Ten of the 16 stakeholders are common to all of the measures used. In all cases the larger no. suggests a higher level of importance and centrality of the stakeholder within the network relative to other nodes with the exception of the degree measurement that simply only counts the number of nodes connected to the stakeholders.

Rank	Stakeholders	Degree	Stakeholders	Eigenvectors	Betweenness Centrality	
1	CCT	48	community	0.53751	CCT	13397.097
2	community	44	SAPS	0.51190	community	9457.429
3	SAPS	42	CCT	0.49392	SAPS	4816.422
4	NSRI	24	NSRI	0.30218	Nature Conservation	1956.600
5	family	20	family	0.28746	ward councillor	720.575
6	JRH	18	JRH	0.24477	CMC	377.237
7	Nature Conservation	14	SABC	0.14782	NSRI	369.730
8	SABC	11	Nature Conservation	0.10553	CCT Biodiversity Management Branch	358.373
9	CMC	9	ward councillor	0.09269	BotSoc	349.258
10	ward councillor	9	Metro Rescue Services	0.07037	CCT Environmental Resources	325.397
11	BotSoc	7	CPF	0.06658	CCT Parks and forests	295.209
12	WCA	7	CMC	0.06112	family	288.892
13	CCT Biodiversity Management Branch	6	CCT Law enforcement	0.05642	CPF	259.598
14	public	6	public	0.05509	CTFRS	221.057
15	CCT Parks and forests	6	WCA	0.05487	Cape Flats Nature	176.851
16	CPF	6	CCT Biodiversity Management Branch	0.05413	SANBI	175.528

that falls outside of the top 16 stakeholder list, when using Betweenness centrality as the centrality measurement. Betweenness centrality can be regarded as a measure of the extent to which an actor has control over information flowing between vertices. Betweenness centrality quantifies the number of times a node acts as a bridge along the shortest path between two other nodes.

The reason for the exclusion of JRH and SABC from the list of stakeholders according to the betweenness centrality measure is thus based on the fact that it did not serve as the shortest path between two other nodes largely due to them being involved in the same reported drowning incident in October and November 2010, constituting a total of 19 articles (Figure 2). These two stakeholders were exclusive to this particular incident and do not feature in any other articles, thus the exclusion from the list using betweenness centrality, as it fails to connect a more diverse collection of incidence, thus decentralising and isolating itself from the network, in spite of their high ranking according to the degree and eigenvector measurements.

Degree or Degree-centrality is based on the idea that the number of “direct relations” an actor has is an important feature of his structural position i.e. the greater the number of connections made to a node, the more central and important the node (actor) is to the network. However as it shows with JRH (degree = 18) and SABC (degree = 11), this

Figure 3: The four most well connected stakeholders within the network according to the SNA based on measures of betweenness centrality, eigenvector centrality, degree and connections between differently themed articles (see table 3 for values), namely, (A) SAPS, (B) the community, (C) the CCT and (D) the department of nature conservation. As in Figure 4 that follows the green lines and nodes represents conservation themed articles, red, those related to crime, safety and security and blue, to those centred on urban planning and socio-economic development.

Figure 4: A connected graph representing the actors (stakeholders) and their relationships, as it relates to the articles theme. Each colour grouping of nodes represents the themes of the articles. Grey nodes represent the stakeholders. It is important to note that the size of the nodes are not determined by any calculation, and have been manually adjusted to emphasise key or central nodes/actors in the graph, such as the 'community' that are most important stakeholders according to all three of the centrality measures in Table 3

measure has limited as it does not give any information as to the relationship between stakeholders and the issues at which they converge at. A high degree value doesn't always mean a stakeholder is more central. It can only tell how many connections it has to other nodes (articles), which in the case of JRH and SABC, report the same incident and articles related to that incident.

Similarly with Eigenvector centrality, which is based on the idea that a relationship to a more interconnected node contributes to the actors (node) own centrality to a greater extent than a relationship to a less well interconnected node (Bonacich and Lloyd, 2001). the problem with the use of eigenvectors in this analysis is that despite its ranking nodes according to how well connected to other well connected nodes, it relies heavily on degree values in determine the measure. And as it has been established, degree-centrality does not accurately describe relationships, it is merely an account of the number of connections.

SAPS, is a problematic stakeholder in terms of using the three above mentioned measures of centrality. It has a high degree measure of 42, a high eigenvector value of 0.51 and a betweenness centrality measure of 4816.42. However the betweenness centrality measurement doesn't explain SAPS centrality accurately. Unlike CCT and the community, SAPS, is almost exclusively connected to articles whose themes are centred on crime, safety and security, with it only being featured in three articles related to conservation and with no direct connections to articles whose theme is urban planning and socio-economic development.

Community and the CCT with the addition of the Nature conservation department (CCT) and the ward councillors are the most central in the network in terms of connecting the reported issues (articles) relating to the themes crime, safety and security, conservation and urban planning and socio-economic development (figure).

Narrative analysis of articles

Analysis of the articles reporting violent crime provides insight into the problems facing the WNR and open spaces on the Cape Flats in general, such as, the notoriety of WNR's bushes and dune systems as a site for violent crime and other criminal act; and secondly, the lack of surveillance and guardianship of the area, contributing to making the reserve a criminal haven. And finally the suggestion that a mistrust that exists between the CCT and law enforcement, and the community.

According to the analysis of the news articles published between 1994 and 2013, articles related to violent crime contributed a large proportion of the total articles

within the theme Crime, safety and security (which is the largest theme category in the analysis).

Violent crimes such as rape and murder, as it relates to WNR, appear to go hand in hand. The victims, who are largely female or young children, are raped and/or murdered, either on site, or disposed of at WNR (Yeld, 1995:12; Ontbossing in Plain sal raad R5,8 M kos Nasorgsentrum vir kinders oorweeg, 1994:7; Body of man with hands and feet tied found on Mnandi rocks, 2006:3; Jacobs, 1997:5; Drie jong meisies in Skiereiland verkrag Man (22) in Mitchell's Plain geskiet , 1995:7; Bonthuys, 2013; Afrika, 2013). These cases are often very violent, as with the victims of the Station Strangler serial killings (Yeld, 1994:12) and the case involving the teenage girl Andrelette Peters from Lentegeur in Mitchell's Plain (Teen stabbed 120 times, 2010). Andrelette Peters left her home in October 2010 to go buy airtime and was never seen alive again. Her body was found three days later on the beach at WNR.

“Her attackers ripped her face to pieces after stabbing her 120 times—the only way this young woman’s mother could identify her was by a tattoo” (Teen stabbed 120 times, 2010). Her mother who was later interviewed said,

“She was stabbed 120 times and her face was in (pieces), the flesh was ripped out. She was stabbed so many times in the face” that, “When the detective took me to the morgue to identify her body, I was not shown her face”.

In 1994 newspapers were running stories on the discovery, of four young boys who were kidnapped, molested and murdered, at WNR (Yeld, 1994; Buitelandse kundige help allig monster jag 1994: 7; Ontbossing in Plain sal raad R5,8 M kos Nasorgsentrum vir kinders oorweeg, 1994: 7). An outraged and fearful community then proceeded to burn and hack about 50 ha of the reserve, on the premise that the bushes and Acacia stands provided cover for the murderer. These murders were part of a string of serial killings of 22 known victims (Bailey, 2005), young boys between the ages of 9 and 12, which took place over the course of nearly a decade, up until 1995, when the alleged killer was apprehended. All of the victims were found with their hands and feet tied together, and their underpants tied tightly around their necks. The killer supposedly kidnapped all of his victims at train stations, such as the Kapteinsklip station adjacent to WNR, hence he was dubbed the “Station Strangler”.

The open spaces around Mitchell's Plain were the primary dumping grounds of the young boys' bodies, with the Wolfgat and Strandfontein dunes having had the highest body count. WNRs popularity as a dumping sight (Bonhuys, 2012) for bodies was reported in the Son newspaper that reported 5 murder incidents that occurred at WNR in 1998, 2008, 2010 and 2011. One of which involved the disposal of a murdered man by three metro police officers in 2011 (Bonthys, 2012).

This string of incidents that constituted the decade-long reign of a serial killer caused fear to mount in the Cape Flats communities, political tensions and an unsafe local environment (open spaces such as WNR included). These ultimately reached breaking point, when the local community felt the need to take action on their own behalf. Their actions forced the municipality, law enforcement and the Law and Order Ministry to get more involved (Yeld, 1994:12), so as to apprehend the killer but also to clear the bushes they believed provided cover to the serial killer.

This mounting pressure exerted by the local community to clear the bushes, forced the municipal Parks and Forest branch to clear the area, at a high cost to the state, estimated at approximately R5.8 million at the time (Ontbossing in Plain sal raad R5,8 M kos Nasorgsentrum vir kinders oorweeg, 1994: 7). Several news articles describe an element of fear and concern felt by the local community and conservation staff, regarding the reserve and adjacent dune systems and its use by criminals (City accused of neglecting its nature reserves, 2008: 4; Prins, 2000:4; Papier, 2012:1; Majiet, 2012:5; Papier, 2011:3). Much of the problem according to the community members and others quoted in the articles lies with how the bush areas have been used for criminal activities. A resident interviewed by a Peoples Post reporter had this to say about the problem,

"Criminals have made the bush their home, creating spaces where they do drugs and conduct other criminal activities. They break into homes in the area and use the bush as an escape route" (Papier, 2012).

Likewise, an interview with the Mitchell's Village Civic Association chairperson revealed a very similar concern,

"We face many challenges from the criminal elements that use the nature reserve as a hiding place to hide stolen goods, and where drug addicts also smoke their drugs, which

poses a fire threat to our beautiful nature reserve” (Papier, 2011).

With the strong criminal presence comes a fear of victimisation experienced by both the neighbouring community and the WNR conservation staff in the field. Conservation staff in an article published on the 14th of July 2008, conservation staff responsible for the City of Cape Town nature reserves accuse the City of neglecting the safety of its conservation staff, particularly in the high risk areas such as the WNR and the Macassar Dunes Conservation Area (MDCA), which are managed by the same team of rangers. These reserves, considered to be turning into “white elephants” due to the lack of security, law enforcement officials and access control to the reserves. The article was written in response to an incident involving the assault of 4 rangers at the MDCA and a growing concern for the safety of the City of Cape Town’s conservation staff (City accused of neglecting its nature reserves, 2008:4). One of the rangers said this of the compromised safety of the staff,

“Before, we used to be able to go into to the reserve every day for four or five hours. Now we are so scared we only go in once or twice a week. As a result the reserve has seen no tourism, no research, no educational projects”.

“We are fearing for our lives. Safety is such a huge factor. We’ve been questioning them (the city) on issues of safety but nothing gets done... What’s the point of having a reserve if you can’t conserve?”

Looking back at Station Strangler murders in 1994 (Yeld, 1994; Die Burger, 1994a b), David Daitz (former director of Parks and Forest branch) came under media fire for comments he made in a meeting with a health and amenities committee where, in response to a question regarding the reserves future, suggested that the reserve may need to be downgraded to a public open space, if there was no community support for the reserve. Before the community hack, community involvement in WNR was largely centred on environmental education programmes, which continue to be the backbone of WNR’s community involvement. This can be seen in 16 articles published since 1995 well up to 2013, that emphasise the use of WNR as an education tool and the push to build a Environmental education centre to service the community (insert reference).

The CCT municipality and law enforcement agencies such as SAPS and Metro

Police are central to addressing the problem of crime, and community and conservation staffs alike have called for increased support from these bodies, to help deal with the problem that is crime, through increased police presence. However, despite their central role of the municipality and law enforcement, mistrust between them and the local community appears to exist. The community has voiced that they feel the CCT has failed them and that law enforcement is ineffective in dealing with the problem of crime, in the area. Even the City's Nature conservation department which falls under the greater CCT municipality governance, voice their concern claiming that the city is neglecting its reserves and staff, putting them at risk of being victimised (City accused of neglecting its nature reserves, 2008:4). This belief that the CCT and law enforcement is failing the community has often resulted in the local community taking action on their behalf in order to address these problems. As with the case of the Station strangler in 1994, where the community cleared the bushes at Wolfgat, because the City had not done so, knowing that the bushes harboured criminal activity. Similarly, community run anti-crime campaigns and groups were established, an example being PAGAD. PAGAD has received significant support from the community, for their strong anti-gang approach, despite being somewhat a vigilante group, whose methods are often violent in nature (Ellis, 2001). The local communities desire for a safe environment, free of crime and violence have lead them to undertake their own crime prevention and anti-crime initiatives such as youth development and neighbourhood watches. Not just to secure their communities but also to ensure that their communities are developed. For the residents of Tafelsig, on the border of WNR, the reserve poses a security threat and is known to harbour criminal activity. Their involvement in securing the reserve particularly on the urban fringe is born out the lack of patrols and law enforcement active on the reserve premises, which allow for crime to permeate in the area (Papier, 2011:3).

The article, "Residents 'take back' Wolfgat Reserve" published in the Peoples Post on the 15th March 2011 (Papier, 2011:3), reported on a collaborative venture between the Tafelsig community (including neighbour watch) and the nature conservation department of CCT, to reclaim the reserve from criminals. It provides insight as to the role of the community in securing the WNR, the concept of community/social control in reducing the pervasiveness of crime. These are some of the quotes made the chairperson of the Mitchell's Village Civic Association, Ricardo

Norton regarding the purpose of undertaking such action:

“We decided to take back our nature reserve from the criminals that give the nature reserve a negative image”.

“We face many challenges from the criminal elements that use the nature reserve as a hiding place to hide stolen goods, and where drug addicts also smoke their drugs, which poses a fire threat to our beautiful nature reserve”.

“It is important that the greater Mitchell’s Plain businesses and communities support us in beautifying our precious nature reserve”.

“Our bio-diversity is under threat and it is everybody’s responsibility to take ownership and responsibility to save our bio-diversity”.

“We should act now or our bio-diversity will be lost forever”.

This operation that was conducted was done so under the guidance of Jerome September, an Environmental Education officer working for nature conservation (City of Cape Town) based at the WNR office in Mitchell’s Plain. He had this to say about the importance and value of this community venture for both WNR conservation and the community:

“These types of ventures are bearing fruit because Nature Conservation does not have the manpower to patrol the reserve on a regular basis”.

“The community is starting to see the value of Wolfgat Nature Reserve, and they are taking ownership of the area bordering the nature reserve,”

“If the bordering residents found value within the nature reserve, then surely benefits can be obtained such as increased property values”.

From this emerges another point and that is the valuing of the reserve by the community.

The community appear to show a great interest in securing the reserve due to what they believe is an asset that could aid the development of their community, and that the biodiversity is there for them to embrace and enjoy. According to many of the articles this appears to be a major motivator, if not the main motivation for securing the reserve, unlike the case involving the Station Strangler, where the prime motivation for community activism, which resulted in the community clearing the bush, was borne out of outrage and fear.

Community members, leaders and other stakeholders share the opinion that the lack of socio-economic development, youth development initiatives and poor living

conditions are contributing to the pervasiveness of crime in the reserve and surrounding area. Unemployment in conjunction with these challenges, are allowing for the criminal economy to thrive in the area.

Issues of development, crime safety and security and conservation appear to inextricably link one another. The link between conservation and urban planning and socio-economic development is established on the basis of WNR being an asset to social and economic development of the Mitchell's Plain community. The link between conservation and development, and crime, safety and security is based on the premise (established in the articles) that crime in the WNR area and the neighbouring community is a threat to conservation and thus the development of the area (Arends, 2002:9; Cruywagen, 1999:12). It is established that criminal presence in the reserve, deters land users as well as creating difficulties for WNR staff, through the generation of fear due to their compromised safety in the field (City accused of neglecting it nature reserves).

Discussion

Results of the newspaper content analysis show that news on crime safety and security comprises the largest proportion of all the articles analysed (see table) as it relates to WNR. Also in addition to WNR being newsworthy in its self (see table), when analysed in relation to the article theme, we find that the higher the level of importance placed on WNR within the article, the more likely it is that the article is about crime, safety and security. The question is then what makes news about crime, safety and security issues concerning Wolfgat so newsworthy.

The social and political impact of crime news is quite broad and thus it is important to understand the forces that shape crime news. Media emphasis on crime often helps maintain the salience of crime as a political issue, as opposed to reflecting changes crime rates (Surette, 1992), and is known to increase citizens' receptivity to strict tough-on-crime policy proposals (Leps, 1992; Scheingold, 1991). Reporting of crime is not dependent on the actual changes in the crime rate, something that must be duly noted by content analysts (Jacob, 1984; Smith, 1984; Lewis, 1993; Scheingold, 1991).

Journalists and editors are most often responsible for selecting which crimes to report and which to ignore, similarly with other types of subject matter reported, whether it be about politics, economics or the environment. Most crimes aren't reported in the news. Research on journalists' selection process has shown that in terms of the type of crime reported, homicide is the most to be reported (Graber, 1980). This too may explain why violent crime and particularly articles related to murder and rape, appear frequently in the dataset a total of 28 times, comprising 30.4% of articles in crime, safety and security and 14% of the total dataset. An informant from the American newspaper, the Tribune, discussed what it is that makes crime newsworthy, and how the ranking of homicides is done according to its appeal to the audience, stating that:

"Death is news. Now I'm not talking about your ordinary, everyday homicide. You need something more. Bullets flying, police shooting, repeated incidents, twisted, weird. It's news. It's what people want to hear".

The most emotive and "newsworthy" news articles such as tragic incidents and

crimes are usually played up; and less "exciting" incidents and crimes usually played down, even though the public has a far greater risk of experiencing them (Smith, 1984). Incidence like the SABC drowning fiasco in 2010 is an example of how more emotive topics, whose tragic nature results in it being more reported and played up. This incident was featured 20 times in the dataset over a period of 24 days, in several newspaper publications (Afrika, 2010). Tragic incidence and particularly drowning at WNR, constitutes 16.8% of the total amount of articles, 20 of which is associated with one incident. Similarly the case involving the 19 year old girl from Lenteguur, Mitchells Plain who was raped and stabbed 120 times beyond recognition and dumped on the WNR (), as well as the serial killings, of the Stations Strangler, who was active in the Cape Flats for nearly a decade.

The construct of deviance that subsumes the most commonly advanced explanations for patterns in crime coverage, based on traditional news criteria such as impact, conflict, prominence, and unusualness, as well as race, and social status. Deviance is a theoretical tool for understanding journalists' decisions regarding the reporting of crime news (Cohen & Young, 1981; Ericson, Baranek, & Chan, 1987), which is based on a centred on the violation of social norms and in most part sensationalism. News itself can be regarded as being atomistic, often incoherent; comprising of historic and decontextualised snippets of current affairs (Alexander, 1981).

It is arguable whether or not the press plays a role in creating awareness of crime, safety and security in the public mind. Word of mouth and interaction between community members is still considered the main conduit in creating awareness. The press most likely doesn't determine in detail how this awareness is shaped. If anything, previous research has shown that the press is quite ineffective in transmitting specific ideas and information (e.g. Robinson, 1972). This however is not always the case. Manuel (2006) found that the Tafelsig and Harare communities bordering Wolfgat Nature Reserve were in fact or at least in part influenced by the news of crime reported by the press. The frequent reporting of crime occurring at Wolfgat, in the press, was found to contribute to the deterring of the communities from using the reserve, due to the negative perception created around the reserve.

The reported articles and associated themes converge and around several central

stakeholders and the concept of development and crime prevention and control. According to Social Network Analysis (SNA) the themes of 'conservation', 'urban planning and socio-economic development' and 'crime safety and security' are linked to one another through four major stakeholders namely, the Mitchell's Plain community, the City of Cape town municipality; SAPS and the CCT Nature conservation department (See figures 3 and 4). Narrative analysis reveals that the three themes of articles converge under the premise of development (social and economic) and crime prevention and control.

The state of development in Mitchell's Plain and WNR

The underdeveloped state of the Mitchell's Plain Township, the high incidence of crime and incivility it experiences, compounded further by high levels of unemployment and the socio-economic isolation of the area, has contributed to WNR experiencing a severe security-threat level due to violent crime (Phelan & Thornhill, 2011).

This risk associated with open areas such as WNR, has provided some of the motivation for its inclusion into the Urban Renewal Programme or URP (EE Unit, 2005) as well as the Cape Renewal Strategy (CRS). The reserves ecological value and the potential socio-economic benefits that it has to offer were also factors contributing to the process of its inclusion (EE Unit, 2005; Manuel, 2006; Walters, 2011).

A development strategy such as with the URP and CRS, incorporates aspects of social, economic and environmental planning as well as policing and crime prevention. It is built upon the cooperation and coordination of multiple stakeholders and organisations, both governmental and non-governmental. Development of Mitchell's Plain and other townships have been slow and difficult. The sheer magnitude of the social challenges such as crime, poverty and high unemployment, appear to quash any attempt of long term development. Developments such as the building of the Wolfgat Environmental Education Centre, which was in planning from as early as 2006 (Manuel, 2006), was a slow process, whose progress was limited by lack of funds poor communication and cooperation between stakeholders. The Edu-centre was then temporarily set up at the Strandfontein Pavilion in the adjacent

suburb. Narrative analysis of the articles also revealed that community members' felt that service delivery was poor and that the CCT and government failed to deliver on their promises. Crime, safety and security concerns have however remained the biggest challenge to development of the community and conservation, through various types of criminal activities, ranging from environmental crime, to those stemming from the social challenges, such as property theft and violent crime ().

The challenge posed by crime

A long list of threats and challenges facing WNRs conservation emerges from the content analysis and identified in the WNR management plan and other official documentation, including environmental threats such as global climate change; threats to biodiversity due to invasive fauna and flora; and urban-development threats such as inappropriate and unauthorised developments along the reserve edge. Other threats to the environment include illegal dune access by 4x4s (insert reference); man-made fires (insert reference), and pollution through illegal dumping (insert reference). However, according to the WNR Management Plan (Walters, 2011), crime, safety and security concerns constitute the majority of the threats facing the reserve (see table), and that these are beyond the control of management. These include threats to personnel safety and intimidation of staff by criminals (Phelan & Thornhill, 2010); increased risk of criminal activity due to uncontrolled access in to WNR (Phelan and Thornhill, 2010; Walters, 2011); a lack of capacity in relevant government departments in the enforcement of law and ensuring security (insert reference), and the increased incidence of crime (see results).

The fear of victimisation is a very important threat facing the conservation staff responsible for WNR. Their compromised safety (see results), prevents them from effectively executing their duties, through limiting when they are able to enter in to the reserve and thus implement the management plan for the reserve, for which field work is essential.

Crime, safety and security concerns need to be addressed effectively in order for the reserve to function optimally. It does, however, require that the lack of coordination and cooperation among government departments (Walters, 2011; Rauch, 2002) and stakeholders, to be resolved. As discussed earlier, crime, safety and security

concerns are inextricably linked to development and conservation issues specifically as it relates to WNR.

Addressing the criminal threat

i) Role of SAPS and the CCT

The threat posed by violent crime towards conservation staff in the Wolfgat area, brought about by its location and proximity to the neighbouring community and the social challenges it faces, is one that is of particular concern, as the lack of safety and security not only prevents the conservation staff from effectively managing and conserving the biodiversity, but prevents developments from taking form and being successful (Khan, 2000; Rauch, 2002; EE Unit, 2005; Eliasson, 2006; Manuel, 2006; Phelan & Thornhill, 2010; Walters, 2011).

Conservation officers and rangers duties are no longer limited to the enforcement of environmental law but have begun incorporating recreational law enforcement. Conservation law enforcement agencies, conservation managers and rangers have been transitioning from a specialised branch of law enforcement focussed on environmental law enforcement and management into a more generalist law enforcement orientation in many places around the world (Falcone, 2004). Officers are expected to take on recreational law enforcement tasks (Morse, 1973; Sherblom, Keranen & Withers, 2002; Eliason, 2006) as well as the more traditional law enforcement tasks, due to greater number of people using public lands for recreational purposes (Walters, 2011), as well as a result of an increase in urban types of crime occurring in these areas (Pendleton, 1998; Pendleton, 2000; Eliason, 2006; Manuel, 2006; Phelan & Thornhill, 2010; Walters, 2011).

Conservation staff at WNR does not possess the authority held by policing bodies such as the South African Police Services (SAPS) or the Metro police. The threats, particularly regarding the safety and security of the staff, lie outside of the control of the conservation staff (Phelan & Thornhill, 2010; Walters, 2011). Thus there is a great need for collaborative efforts between conservation departments and law enforcement (Manuel, 2006; Phelan & Thornhill, 2010; Walters, 2011; EE Unit, 2005). According to the SNA, SAPS is the most important stakeholder as it relates to the theme of Crime, safety and security (as it's connected to a large proportion of the

reported issues under the theme) (see figure). Along with law enforcement they are responsible for securing the City's urban and ecological areas. However their role is questionable. They are undoubtedly important however they do have limitations.

The role of the defence and police forces in development has been and continues to be, a contentious issue since the democratisation of South Africa (Cawthra, 1997; Samara, 2011). In his book "Securing South Africa's Democracy", Cawthra (1997) poses several questions as to their role in development. "Do they soak up resources which might otherwise be directed towards developing the nation or are they a modernisation force?" And "Do they stabilise and widen the base of government or destabilise and narrow it?" SAPS have the primary constitutional function in the prevention of crimes in the country and thus all communities in Cape Town, Mitchell's Plain. The CCT works in conjunction with SAPS, though collaborations with the City's law enforcement agencies namely the Metro police, but mainly functions as the primary source of governance in the City, owed to their jurisdictional administrative power. Secondly, City authorities work closely with businesses and private security companies to implement the city's urban security management strategies-, familiar to residents of many aspiring world-class cities-, for the purpose of reclaiming and revitalising core urban spaces, including the townships (Samara, 2011). However despite the efforts to develop these urban spaces, the process of reclaiming and revitalisation, has instead contributed to the reproduction of the inequalities that marks the differences between the central city and the townships of Cape Town (Samara, 2011:4). This division between township and the central city is the fundamental socio-spatial division of the city, one that marks its political character that has persisted in the post-Apartheid South Africa (Samara, 2011:4).

The approach that the City has taken to urban security is not illogical, considering its context. One that is, earmarked as it is by neoliberal economic development, which has been adopted post-Apartheid by the state. Neoliberal governance, its definition of development and the related security requirements plays an important role in the urban renewal and development processes within the townships such as Mitchell's Plain and the affluent areas within the city (Samara, 2011:4).

The policing of open spaces like the WNR (a strategic point in the URP and the CRS) is thus of great importance to securing the reserve. However the police have not

shown to be effective in addressing crime (according to the narrative analysis), due to a poor presence (a result of under-staffing, limited resources, low prioritisation of the reserve, etc.) in the area (Thornhill and Phelan, 2010; Walters, 2011) as well as their inability to tackle crime at the point of origin (Cawthra, 1997; Rauch, 2002; Samara, 2011). Alternatives to our society's dependence should thus be considered.

ii) Land use and social control

The use of protected areas and vacant land for crimes, such as drug use, prostitution and violent crime, can pose a serious problem for conservation management as established in the narrative analysis (refer to results). The more vacant and vegetated an area of land (such as the bushes referred to in the narrative analysis) the more it seems to be preferred for drug use, rape and other violent crimes, by providing cover for criminals to commit the crimes (). Vacant land has been seen as a contributing factor to these criminal activities (South African Cities Network, 2003). The WNR to the South of Tafelsig is one the vacant areas, experiences such criminal activities (CCT, 2009).

Vacant land, such as the WNR, has been posited to have a significant association with higher incidence of crime (Ley & Cybriwsky, 1974; Greenberg, Rohe & Williams, 1982; LaGrange, 1999), deemed to be a result of increased level of opportunity that exists in the absence of guardianship or informal control and the lack of surveillance and law enforcement (Stucky & Ottensmann, 2009; Walters, 2011). It is argued that nature of the place, such as landscape, spatial features and location relative to other areas of high crime, constitute opportunities for crime (Eck, 2001; Phelan & Thornhill, 2010; Caplan *et al.*, 2013). Additionally crimes are not equally distributed across locations, often forming hotspots (Block & Block, 1995; Eck & Weisburd, 1995; Weisburd & Mazerolle, 2000; Braga & Weisburd, 2010; Caplan *et al.*, 2013). Wolfgat with its lack of patrols, poor surveillance, uncontrolled access, the social challenges faced by the neighbouring community, the absence of guardianship and the lack of informal control in terms of public lack of willingness to exercise control and participate (Manuel, 2006; Phelan & Thornhill, 2010; Walters, 2011) has contributed to the high levels of crime, particularly violent crime, that the area experiences. Combined with the environmental features such as dune systems and the dense

vegetation and alien cover (Acacias) that provide criminals with cover have contributed to its hotspot status.

Many studies under the assumption that land uses such as industrial, agricultural and natural areas, have direct effects on crime irrespective of social context wherein that land use occurs, conclude that the effects of these non-residential areas on crimes was expected to be the same in both advantaged and disadvantaged areas, a rather unwarranted assumption. The argument against it is based on the grounds that despite creating the opportunity for crime, socio-economic characteristics of the area, and the occupants' willingness to exercise social control over it will determine how the land use will contribute to crime (Merry, 1981; Smith, Frazee & Davison, 2000; Wilcox *et al.*, 2004; Stucky & Ottensmann, 2009). Exercising social control over an area forms part of a process of creating a defensible space.

Community involvement in WNR is still limited primarily to environment education initiatives and cleaning campaigns. Despite the claim in the WNR Management Plan SWOT analysis that "strong community involvement" is strength in addition to having active community partner groups, large-scale community involvement is yet to occur (NB! The WNR MP does not explain what the "strong community entails").

This lack of large-scale community action in terms of willingness and inability to exercise social control over the area appears to contribute to the persistence of crime in spite of the social and economic development initiatives that have been implemented in the area concerning WNR, possibly due to the sheer magnitude of the socio-economic and social challenges facing the community (Rauch, 2002). A theory exists which posits that community crime rates vary because of the social structural factors, including poverty, ethnic heterogeneity and family instability, impede the ability of residents to maintain informal social control in the neighbourhood, known as social disorganisation theory (Bursik, 1988; Stucky & Ottensmann, 2009).

The physical environment and land use have a significant effect on the occurrence of crime as well as the nature of that crime (Kuo & Sullivan, 2001; EE Unit, 2005; Stucky & Ottensmann, 2009; Phelan & Thornhill, 2010). The state of the physical environment is not, however, causal to the crime: it merely provides a setting. It is

the role of the community wherein that area occurs, in terms of its social structural that determines the outcome. Social control of an area, by a community requires an incentive, one that is not necessarily economic, such as crime control and prevention. At WNR we see this in the form of neighbourhood watches and community police forums (CPFs).

iii) Community involvement in the safety and security of WNR and its implications on conservation

The South African environmental movement has dramatically changed from its former elitist image that was prominent in the apartheid and colonial rule, to make major strides in reaching the broader spectrum of its society. This has not, however, been a smooth transition. The country's long and bitter history of racism and racial conflict dating back to mid-17th century, has had effects on South African society that has had long lasting impacts that negatively influence the attitudes of historically marginalised black communities toward environmental issues. The combined effect of racially discriminatory laws and stringent conservation regulations that excluded native and rural peoples resulted in the alienation of black communities from the environmental sphere and conservation (Khan, 2000; Manuel, 2006; Struwig, 2010).

Communities who benefit from Protected Areas (PAs) are more likely to express positive attitudes towards conservation (Manuel, 2006). The unequal distribution of benefits, results in the persistence of negative attitudes towards PAs in spite of the benefits (Parry & Campbell, 1992; Manuel, 2006). Socio-economic factors, discussed in earlier sections, such as ethnicity, religion, age, gender, education, and living distance from the PA's are important determinants of people's attitude towards PAs, or urban natural environments, like WNR (Infield, 1988; 1998; Khan, 2000; Manuel, 2006; Struwig, 2010).

Manuel (2006) found that in terms of attitudes held of the WNR and its management by the neighbouring communities, that the greatest criticism, which received 83 % of support from community leaders, was that WNR officials did not protect citizens from crime occurring in the PA. Additionally residents of the interviewed communities,

Tafelsig and Harare, stated that the major drawback preventing them from using the area was the threat of crime and gangsterism. Tafelsig residents also cited the lack of patrols and law enforcement and the thick bush created by invasive alien plants as the respective third and fourth drawbacks, with dumping of waste as second (Manuel, 2006).

Community neighbourhood watches and CPFs are involved in all of these drawbacks as they relate to WNR, as found in the newspaper article analysis (Yeld, 1994; Jacobs, 1997; Independent Newspapers, 1999; Ells, 2001; Plainsman, 2011a; Papier, 2011; van der Fort, 2011). Their involvement in securing the reserve particularly on the urban fringe is born out the lack of patrols and law enforcement active on the reserve premises. Conservation staff has thus built working relationships, to help improve the security of the area. Interestingly the role of the neighbourhood watch receives very little attention within the WNR's Management Plan, The City of Cape Town Security Audit, and the Environmental Management Framework for the area (EE Unit, 2005; Phelan & Thornhill, 2010; Walters, 2011).

Community participation in the form of neighbourhood watches and police and community collaborations in the form of CPFs, as it incentivises the community to involve themselves in the securing of the reserve area, which is beneficial to both the community and the conservation staff who utilise it. However the history of these collaborative efforts between the state, police services and the community has been very poor. Community initiatives such as CPFs and neighbourhood watches have received very little support in terms of financial capital and state resources, compared to hard policing, such as SAPS and Metro Police services (Rauch, 2002; Samara, 2010; Samara, 2011). Samara (2011) and Cawthra (1997) both supported the idea that community anti-crime initiatives are better suited to secure areas than hard policing which requires significantly higher amounts of resource input. However because community development initiatives, youth development programmes and community anti-crime initiatives often take longer than most political terms to bear fruit, they often fail due to lack of state and political support (Samara, 2011). This is because the availability of resources change, along with the changes made in political offices. Politicians have differences in what they prioritise and what is

expected of them by those who elected them to office (Samara, 2011). This results in the disruption between the collaborative efforts between government departments and stakeholders which threatens the survival of development initiatives, community anti-crime initiatives and conservations, as is the case with WNR (Cawthra, 1997; Manuel, 2006; Samara, 2010; Walters, 2011).

It is of high importance to the conservation of WNR that community initiatives not only be incentivised but that a stable support structure exists that will help it persist. This will contribute to the willingness of the community (“occupants”) to exercise social control of the area, thereby regulating and determining how the reserve will contribute to crime (Manuel, 2006; Walters, 2011; Samara, 2011). Community involvement and collaboration with other government institutions in such matters has shown to decrease the frequency of crime and encourage the use of natural and open spaces that may have otherwise been avoided, as is the case with WNR (Kuo & Sullivan, 2001; Manuel, 2006; Stucky & Ottensmann, 2009). The Management Plan for WNR (Walters, 2011) encourages the concept of community involvement, ownership and social control. This holds true for several other management frameworks developed for the area, where prevention of crime and the conservation future is contingent on the involvement of community in the management and development process (EE Unit, 2005; Phelan & Thornhill, 2010; Walters, 2011).

Social crime prevention (and reduction) strategies, such as neighbourhood watches and youth development programmes, are given very little media attention, as opposed to police cordons and search operations, as they do not generally involve newsworthy events and in terms of crime rates, it is difficult to measure their effects (Rauch, 2002; Samara, 2011). This may explain the lack of articles related to community/social crime prevention (and reduction) strategies involving neighbourhood watches, where of the 190 articles in the dataset, only 4 made a reference to them. Of the four, 2 were in reference to funding allocation to Mitchell’s Plain initiatives such as neighbourhood watch training (Van der Fort, 2013), the monitoring of illegal dumping (Mazwayi, 2010), the murder incident involving a former Pagad member (Ellis, 2001) and the other regarding a crime blitz undertaken by the local civic organisation and the neighbourhood watch (Papier, 2011).

The key to controlling crime, within the context of the conservation of WNR and Mitchell's Plain, would thus appear to lay with the local community and their undertakings in social crime prevention and reduction strategies, such as with neighbourhood watches and development initiatives. However, social crime prevention and reduction strategies, receive very little backing from government, in spite of the encouragement given to communities, to reclaim their neighbourhoods, particularly in areas of the cape flats (Samara, 2011).

Social crime prevention strategies differ in comparison to hard policing in the form of SAPS and Metro Police, in that their purpose is to tackle the causal factors of crime, as opposed to politically fuelled, crime crackdowns on communities which fail to resolve the social, economic and environmental factors that are conducive to particular kinds of crime (Stucky & Ottensmann, 2009; Samara, 2011).

The success of an urban nature reserve such as WNR is thus highly contingent on the success of the community to which it is adjoined. The challenges that Mitchells Plain faces have and will continue to effect the conservation of reserve. It is thus imperative that conservation and social and economic development be aligned. It is difficult to separate the criminal threats facing the reserve and the community from the development of the area, as the perpetuation of crime is so strongly attributed to underdevelopment and the lack of social control exercised by the community. Therefore I would argue that for the criminal threat faced by the WNR to be addressed effectively the local community needs to be mobilised to take control of the area, by enforcing social control, in so deterring criminals from utilising the reserve thus improving not only there safety, but that of the conservation staff, whom too will benefit. But in order for this to work there needs to be a stable cooperative effort between the community the City and local government and law enforcement, through meeting development needs and support for community crime prevention and reduction groups and organisations.

Conclusion

The use of newspaper content analysis to explore the impact that the social challenge of crime facing the conservation of WNR and the neighbouring community poses many difficulties mainly due to the nature of news which doesn't reflect the crime rate, and the way crime news in particular is selected. News about crime and particularly homicide is given the most attention as it is more emotive and attractive to the audience. However when combined with social network analysis and narrative analysis of the news articles, revealed greater insights in to the challenge that crime poses to conservation. Narrative analysis along with SNA allows one to create a context and establish a basis on which the issues reported in the news relate to one another.

The success of an urban nature reserve such as WNR is thus highly contingent on the success of the community to which it is adjoined. The challenges that Mitchells Plain faces have and will continue to effect the conservation of reserve. It is thus imperative that conservation and social and economic development be aligned. It is difficult to separate the criminal threats facing the reserve and the community from the development of the area, as the perpetuation of crime is so strongly attributed to underdevelopment and the lack of social control exercised by the community. Therefore I would argue that for the criminal threat faced by the WNR to be addressed effectively the local community needs to be mobilised to take control of the area, by enforcing social control, in so deterring criminals from utilising the reserve thus improving not only there safety, but that of the conservation staff, whom too will benefit.

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